

BAMBOO

D2.1: Benchmarking of available flexibility management tools for REI 12/2018 (M04)

D2.1: Second draft version

Authors: Arnaud Rouanet (N-SIDE)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820771. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

BAMBOO

Technical References

Project Acronym	BAMBOO
Project Title	Boosting new Approaches for flexibility Management By Optimizing process Off-gas and waste use
Project Coordinator	Cristina Gonzalo Tirado Fundación CIRCE cgonzalo@fcirce.es
Project Duration	September 2018 - March 2022

Deliverable No.	D2.1
Dissemination level ¹	PU
Work Package	WP 2 - Characterization and management of the plants' flexibility
Task	T 2.6 - Assessment on flexibility management tools and main requirements for DSS modules
Lead beneficiary	7 (N-SIDE)
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	1 (CIRCE), (4) IKERLAN, (12) COSMO
Due date of deliverable	31/12/2018
Actual submission date	14/01/2019

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820771. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

Document history		
V	Date	Beneficiary partner(s)
0	16/11/2018	N-SIDE
1	27/11/2018	CIRCE
2	14/12/2018	N-SIDE
3	19/12/2018	CIRCE
4	02/01/2019	N-SIDE
5	08/01/2019	CIRCE
6	10/01/2019	N-SIDE

DISCLAIMER OF WARRANTIES

This document has been prepared by BAMBOO project partners as an account of work carried out within the framework of the EC-GA contract no 820771.

Neither Project Coordinator, nor any signatory party of BAMBOO Project Consortium Agreement, nor any person acting on behalf of any of them:

- a. makes any warranty or representation whatsoever, express or implied,
 - i. with respect to the use of any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document, including merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose, or
 - ii. that such use does not infringe on or interfere with privately owned rights, including any party's intellectual property, or
 - iii. that this document is suitable to any particular user's circumstance; or
- b. assumes responsibility for any damages or other liability whatsoever (including any consequential damages, even if Project Coordinator or any representative of a signatory party of the BAMBOO Project Consortium Agreement, has been advised of the possibility of such damages) resulting from your selection or use of this document or any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document.

Table of content

1	<u>EXECUTIVE SUMMARY</u>	5
2	<u>INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES</u>	6
3	<u>SCOPE OF BAMBOO DSS TOOL</u>	7
3.1	MAIN OBJECTIVES OF BAMBOO DSS TOOL	7
3.2	PRELIMINARY IDENTIFICATION OF EXISTING FLEXIBILITY MANAGEMENT TOOLS	8
4	<u>METHODOLOGY</u>	9
5	<u>IDENTIFICATION OF RELEVANT TOOLS</u>	10
5.1	ENERGY FLEXIBILITY VALORIZATION	10
5.2	INDUSTRIAL PROCESS OPTIMIZATION	12
5.3	ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS (EMS)	12
5.4	SUMMARY OF SELECTED TOOLS	13
6	<u>BENCHMARKING OF SELECTED TOOLS</u>	14
6.1	N-SIDE ENERTOP	14
6.1.1	SHORT DESCRIPTION	14
6.1.2	MAIN FEATURES	15
6.1.3	MAIN LIMITATIONS	16
6.2	ABB CPMPLUS ENERGY MANAGER	16
6.2.1	SHORT DESCRIPTION	16
6.2.2	MAIN FEATURES	16
6.2.3	MAIN LIMITATIONS	17
6.3	ARTELYS CRYSTAL INDUSTRY	17
6.3.1	SHORT DESCRIPTION	17
6.3.2	MAIN FEATURES	18
6.3.3	MAIN LIMITATIONS	19
6.4	INNOVATIVE FEATURES FOR BAMBOO DSS TOOL	19
7	<u>CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS</u>	21
8	<u>REFERENCES</u>	22
	<u>ANNEX 1 - DETAILED ANALYSES</u>	23

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

As part of the BAMBOO project objectives, a holistic Decision Support System tool will be developed that will allow valorization of industrial flexibility such as waste streams recycling, fuel switching or electrical load shifting. The DSS tool shall gather energy market scenarios, material flows characterization, waste heat flows assessment, fuel and raw material prices forecast, investment recommendations as well as plant scheduling and planning, in a cross-sectorial solution.

In order to make the most out of this development and integrate innovative features, an initial benchmarking analysis has been performed of selected existing commercial tools allowing to valorize an industrial site flexibility. Initially, a broad gathering of potentially relevant tools has been made from web research and knowledge sharing with the project consortium partners. From these many tools, the most relevant ones were selected considering the objectives of BAMBOO DSS tool. Three solutions were selected at that stage for further analysis: N-SIDE Enertop (which is the basis upon which BAMBOO DSS tool will be developed), ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager and Artelys Crystal Industry.

For each of these tools, an analysis of functionalities and features was performed based on publicly available information, as detailed as possible considering the limitation of information. These analyses served as basis for a benchmarking of these tools' features, comparing N-SIDE Enertop to the other two platforms. From this comparison, the most innovative and relevant features to be added to Enertop in the development of BAMBOO DSS tool were identified: direct data connection, dashboards and flexible timescales, amongst other examples.

2 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

In the scope of BAMBOO project, one of the important objectives resides in the valorization of industrial energy flexibility to optimize energy use and compensate renewable energy sources unpredictability, as a way to reduce fossil fuels consumption and greenhouse gases emissions.

Towards this goal, BAMBOO aims at developing a holistic Decision Support System management tool that will characterize and model electrical, heat and material flows towards hourly operation management optimization and investment recommendations for flexibility valorization. The DSS tool shall gather energy market scenarios, material flows characterization, waste heat flows assessment, fuel and raw material prices forecast, investment recommendations as well as plant scheduling and planning, in a cross-sectorial solution.

BAMBOO DSS tool will be built upon the already commercial tool Enertop, developed by the company N-SIDE, based in Belgium. Enertop is an energy flexibility valorization platform that optimizes industrial processes production planning to leverage their flexibility with respect to fluctuating energy market prices.

As a first step towards the development of BAMBOO DSS tool, a benchmark analysis of existing flexibility management tools is performed in this report, as a way to determine some innovative features that could be integrated in the final tool, improving the existing Enertop platform.

In Chapter 3, the scope of BAMBOO DSS tool is clarified, based on some extracts from BAMBOO Grant Agreement, while Chapter 4 briefly explains the methodology that has been followed. Then, in Chapter 5, a list of commercial tools more or less related to energy flexibility valorization is drawn, from which the most relevant are identified based on the assessment of their core functionalities from a web review. The actual benchmarking of the selected tools with respect to BAMBOO objectives, and summary of interesting innovative tools, is performed in Chapter 6. The benchmarking is based on detailed analyses of information gathered from the suppliers' websites, which are available in Annex 1. Finally, Chapter 7 draws some conclusions and highlights the next steps that will be required to deepen the analysis and determine the main requirements and features that will be integrated in BAMBOO DSS tool.

3 SCOPE OF BAMBOO DSS TOOL

Summary of the main objectives and required features of BAMBOO DSS tool, as identified in the early project phases

3.1 Main objectives of BAMBOO DSS Tool

As a way to efficiently valorize the energy flexibility of REII industrial plants, BAMBOO project aims at developing a *Decision Support tool for flexibility management in an hourly basis and covering all the energy and material vectors in the plant for a full exploitation of its flexibility potential.*

The DSS tool will model of the electrical, heat and material flows within the plant, as well as the energy and raw materials markets, including market forecasts, to simulate the whole environment and interaction. This model will be used for two main actions:

1. **Hourly operation management optimization:** process schedule, streams recycling and energy and raw material purchases, within the process constraints and considering energy and raw material price forecasts.
2. **Flexibility investment recommendations:** based on the simulated Return of Investment (ROI) of these investments.

The Operation Management Optimization module core features identified in this description are summarized below:

- a. Hourly optimization of...
- b. the process operation schedules, including:
 - a. Production planning,
 - b. Energy purchase, generation and consumption,
 - c. Raw material supply,
 - d. Waste streams and by-products recycling and valorization,
- c. based on a complete model of the industrial process, including all relevant energy and material flows (fuels, electricity, steam, waste heat and streams...) using surrogate models of the relevant processes and technologies
- d. and on forecasts of future market prices (fuel, energy, raw material) and/or energy production from local Renewable Energy Sources (RES) assets.

The Flexibility Investment Recommendations module core features, as identified in the scope of BAMBOO project are:

- a. Long-term simulation of...
- b. The Return on Investment (ROI) of flexibility potential enhancement investments,
- c. Through a simulation of the enhanced process based upon the current process model used in the Operation Management Optimization module.

3.2 Preliminary identification of existing flexibility management tools

In the early phases of BAMBOO project, a preliminary identification has been performed of the relevant existing commercial tools for flexibility management. Five software solutions were identified in this first phase, listed in Table 1 below, which will serve as first basis for the identification of the relevant tool in Chapter 5.

Table 1: Preliminary identified tools for flexibility management

Tool	Description
ABB cpM Plus Energy Manager	cpM Plus Energy Manager includes planning and scheduling tools to optimize energy use and supply, energy balance management tools to support the real-time monitoring and control of the energy balance, and reporting tools to evaluate and report energy consumption, costs, efficiency and other energy-related information.
Siemens SIMATIC	SIMATIC tools enable energy management at industrial level. The most relevant, SIMATIC Energy Manager PRO, carries out the evaluation of the different equipment status, obtaining information about energy consumption and thus optimizing the production process and the energy purchase.
N-SIDE ENERTOP	ENERTOP is a decision-aid solution deployable from strategic to real-time operations, providing key information to operate the flexible processes optimally. It is able to increase industries flexibility potential by optimizing choices in terms of investments on new assets or technologies (e.g. power2heat, power2gas, storage,...) and in terms of electricity contracts/market exposure.
Artelys Crystal Industry	Developed within the CitInES project, this tool aids in the design of production planning strategies, by modelling the plant using the available library assets and providing the optimal operation route to maximize energy savings. It has been tested on one of Tupra's refineries.
N-SIDE SCOOP	SCOOP covers the entire value chain of steel production, from raw material selection to end product portfolio. It features procurement, process and product portfolio optimization, as well as investment assessment, in order to maximize the profit of the plant. It also allows the optimization of the entire plant or a single selected unit.

4 METHODOLOGY

Description of the methodology followed for gathering the information, along with the procedure for classifying and comparing the different tools

1. Identification of relevant tools to be integrated in the benchmarking analysis [Chapter 5]:
 - a. Preliminary identification of potentially relevant tools
 - b. Categorization of the identified tools (in three main categories)
 - c. Selection, from the preliminary list, of the tools that are actually relevant to be included in the benchmarking analysis, considering the scope and objectives of BAMBOO DSS tool. The selected tools shall provide operational planning optimization towards energy flexibility valorization and cost minimization, based on a process modelling including all relevant energy and material flows.
2. Extensive gathering of information and detailed analyses on each of the selected tools' functionalities and features, based on web research on the supplier's websites and other relevant sources [References in Chapter 8 and detailed analyses in Annex 1 - Detailed Analyses]
3. Benchmarking of the selected tools [Chapter 0]:
 - a. Summary of their main functionalities, features and limitations
 - b. Innovative features that could be integrated in BAMBOO DSS tool

5 IDENTIFICATION OF RELEVANT TOOLS

Selection of the relevant tools to be included in the benchmarking analysis

This chapter contains the results of the preliminary identification of tools, and the selection of the relevant tools to be integrated in the benchmarking analysis. After a large browsing of potential tools, three categories were identified: Energy Flexibility Valorization, Industrial process optimization and Energy Management Systems (EMS). Each of these identified categories is explained below, with the list of tools that were analyzed. At the end of this chapter is summarized the list of tools eventually selected for the benchmarking analysis.

5.1 Energy flexibility valorization

The field of energy flexibility valorization tools encompasses a variety of different purposes and methods, which differ in terms of target groups, timescale and approaches. The three main target groups identified here are:

- **Generation:** utilities & power production assets, including renewable energy sources
- **Industrial:** electro-intensive sites with or without local power generation
- **Aggregation:** of residential, tertiary and/or small industrial loads, micro-grids

Secondly, they differ in terms of timescale, the three main ones identified below. Within the scope of BAMBOO project, only *Day-Ahead* and *Real-time* scales are considered relevant, based on the objectives summarized in section 3.1.

- **Real-time** = imbalance management (with or without leveraging imbalance price)
- **Day-ahead** = production planning optimization for optimal power nomination or bidding
- **Long-term** = investment & operational strategies recommendations

Finally, and most importantly, different approaches for flexibility valorization have been identified, which are listed below. From these 4 identified approaches, A. and B. correspond to BAMBOO DSS tool main objectives as stated in section 3.1, based on industrial processes models towards the optimization of their energy supply by leveraging their flexibility sources. On the other hand, approaches C. and D. do not consider the internal streams and assets of industrial processes, and consider flexibility valorization from a more abstract and solely market-oriented perspective. For this reason, only tools based on approaches A. and B. are identified as relevant for BAMBOO, in the last column of Table 2.

- Operation management optimization:** valorization of the process energy flexibility on the fluctuating energy markets, through local optimization of the production schedules towards energy cost minimization
- Investment recommendations:** what-if scenarios analyses to compare investments towards energy flexibility increase, based on process modelling
- Virtual Power Plant (VPP):** combination of a group of consumption sites (residential / industrial) for market and ancillary services valorization through aggregation

D. **Power trading optimization:** optimization of the valorization of power production between different markets (ancillary, DA, imbalance), possibly with robotic trading

In Table 2 below are listed the selected tools for energy flexibility valorization that were identified, each with its approach, timescale and target group. Based on these indications, and considering the analysis made in the previous paragraph, the three first of tools of this list were identified as relevant for integration in BAMBOO benchmarking analysis.

Table 2: Selected energy flexibility valorization tools

Tool name	Approach	Timescale	Target	Relevant
N-SIDE Enertop ¹	Operation management optimization (complete energy & production process)	Day-ahead, Long-term	Industrial, Generation	Yes
ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager ²	Energy Management System (EMS), Operation management optimization (complete energy & production process)	Real-time, Day-ahead	Industrial	Yes
Artelys Crystal Industry ³	Operation management optimization (complete energy process) Investment recommendations	Day-ahead, Long-term	Generation, Industrial	Yes
Dexter Energy Services ⁴	Operation management optimization (for individual asset, only imbalance)	Real-time	Generation, Industrial	No(real-time)
Powel Smart Energy Suite ⁵	Virtual Power Plant, Power trading optimization	Day-ahead, Long-term	Generation, Aggregation	No
AutoGrid VPP ⁶	Virtual Power Plant	Real-time	Generation, Aggregation	No
Senfal Industry ⁷	Power trading optimization (robotic trading)	Real-time, Day-ahead	Generation, Industrial	No

¹ <https://www.n-side.com/solution/industrial-energy-flexibility-optimization-2/>

² <https://new.abb.com/cpm/energy-manager>

³ <https://www.artelys.com/en/applications/artelys-energy-planner>

⁴ <https://www.dexterenergy.nl/>

⁵ <https://www.powel.com/solutions/energy/>

⁶ <https://www.auto-grid.com/>

⁷ <https://senfal.com/en/>

5.2 Industrial process optimization

The second category initially considered in the identification of relevant tools was the *industrial process optimization tools*. In this category are considered solutions that take industrial processes or supply chain optimization essentially from a production perspective, rather than oriented towards the energy markets. Examples of tools falling into this category are given in Table 3.

When reviewing the features and functionalities of these tools, it appears that they are usually very process-specific, hence not cross-sectorial. Moreover, the consideration of flexibility valorization through joined optimization of process planning and energy markets is not integrated. Thereby, the relevance of these tools in the benchmarking of flexibility management tools is limited, which is why these tools will not be considered in the benchmark analysis.

Table 3: Examples of Industrial process optimization tools

Supplier	Tool	Field
N-SIDE	Scoop	Steel production & supply chain
AnyLogic	AnyLogic Simulation Software	Supply chain, Industrial processes, Oil&Gas, Mining...
AVEVA	various	Industrial process design, supply chain
Siemens	Tecnomatix	Industry 4.0

5.3 Energy management systems (EMS)

The third category of industrial software solutions initially considered is the Energy Management Systems (EMS). As for the Industrial Process Optimization tools, the EMS were eventually discarded from the analysis, as their relevance for BAMBOO DSS tool appeared limited.

Several suppliers offer Energy Management Systems, which are intended mainly for real-time monitoring of the energy consumption of their industrial assets or buildings. It thus appeared that EMS are essentially related to real-time monitoring and reporting, which is not the focus of BAMBOO DSS tool development. The non-exhaustive list in Table 4 summarizes a selection of such tools. Due to their limited relevance for BAMBOO, these Energy Management tools shall not be integrated in the following benchmark analysis.

Table 4: Examples of Energy Management Systems

Supplier	Tool	Field of application
ABB	cpmPlus Energy Manager	Industrial plant
Siemens	SIMATIC Energy Manager PRO	Industrial plant
Dapesco	JOOL	Residential / Tertiary
Opinum	Opisense	Energy production & Utilities
Enprove	Energy Monitoring & Analytics	Industrial plant / Buildings

5.4 Summary of selected tools

As detailed in this preliminary analysis, it appears that only tools from the Energy Flexibility Valorization category are actually relevant, considering the objectives of BAMBOO DSS tool. Within this category, only some of the approaches considered for flexibility management and optimization timescale have been selected. Eventually, three tools were selected as particularly relevant:

1. N-SIDE Enertop
2. ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager
3. Artelys Crystal Industry

These three software solutions share the approach of optimizing the energy supply of an industrial site through modelling and simulation. In Chapter 6, the features of each of these tools are analyzed, in order to identify innovative feature for BAMBOO DSS tool.

6 BENCHMARKING OF SELECTED TOOLS

This chapter summarizes the main aspects of each of the three selected tools, and extracts the key findings and innovative features to support the development of BAMBOO DSS tool. The extensive analyses performed on each one of the tools, are available in Annex 1 - Detailed Analyses.

6.1 N-SIDE EnerTOP

6.1.1 Short description

The primary purpose of EnerTOP platform is the optimization of operational process & energy purchases schedule in order to leverage the plant's flexibilities to minimize the total energy cost (storage, energy arbitrage...). This is done using a mathematical model of the process, integrating all relevant flexibility sources, production constraints, energy & material flows.

EnerTOP is based on the combination of:

- Mathematical **modelling** of the plant process, material & energy flows and flexibilities;
- Direct connection or integration of relevant **forecasts** (power market price...);
- Advanced **optimization algorithm** to leverage flexibilities for total cost minimization (including energy, raw material, storage cost, grid cost...).

Based on the model of the process, and forecasts of future market prices, the optimization algorithm computes the optimal process schedule that minimizes the total cost of operations.

6.1.1.1 Process modelling

The abstraction of the process modelling is flexible, and can be more or less detailed towards an optimal trade-off between model accuracy and computation cost. Surrogate models are therefore used in place of detailed internal models, representing assets or even sub-processes when relevant. Linear or piece-wise linear models are used, due to the constraints of the MILP (Mixed Integer Linear Programming) optimization method that is used. In addition, parts of the process that do not have any substantial flexibility can be modelled by simple constraints, and non-relevant assets can be neglected (e.g. very short-term storage assets, when optimizing with hourly time steps).

The built-in library allows a large variety of assets and constraints to be modelled, including but not limited to:

- Models of flexible loads and processes, generators, storage, power grid and tariffs...
- Constraints on stock level, flow rates, production rates...
- Constraints on allowed switching on or off of assets, start-up / shutdown costs...
- Asset unavailability during maintenance, night shifts...
- Hourly production requirements for the process end-products
- Contract modelling

Assets and constraints are modelled and challenged using historical data, for best accuracy.

6.1.1.2 Forecasting

Market prices for most energy sources, such as power or gas, are usually not known in advance when the process operation schedule is defined. Therefore, the optimization relies on forecasted price to determine how to best leverage the process flexibility, and propose an optimal power consumption schedule that will serve as basis for power nominations. Market forecasts can be directly integrated to Enertop, for markets such as the electricity Day-Ahead (DA) or Intraday market, or imbalance prices. Machine-learning algorithms are used to design the price forecasts, and foresee as accurately as possible the next day or next hour.

6.1.1.3 Flexibility Optimization

The complete modelling of the plant process, combined with the integrated forecasts, enable the valorization of most flexibility types, towards total cost minimization:

- Load shifting, using the combination of storage units and production over-capacity to schedule production at times of low energy cost;
- Arbitrage between energy sources: for example, electricity from local production or power grid, or heat from a boiler, a waste heat flow or a CHP...
- Optimal electricity purchase and sale from/to the grid following the DA market price fluctuations, based on price forecasts. This is applicable, more generally, to all energy or material flow that is purchased or sold from/to a fluctuating market (natural gas, heat...)

Using Mixed Integer Linear Programming, the complete process is simultaneously optimized, considering all energy & material flows, production requirements and process constraints. The main use case of Enertop consists in a hourly optimization of next days operations, based on DA power market price forecast.

On top of the process model and the forecasts, several operational data are integrated as basis of the optimization, such as hourly demand of the process end-products. For this reason, Enertop allows direct data connection (via REST API) to relevant external databases (forecasting platform, local production planning tools...)

6.1.2 Main features

- Modular structure providing flexibility and adaptability to specific customer needs, and enabling rapid integration of additional ad-hoc models or constraints;
- Data connection to external platforms and databases via REST API (for data input);
- Generic asset library, allowing to model approximately any asset based on linear or piecewise-linear surrogate models;
- Consideration of multiple energy vectors: electricity, fuels, steam, heat...
- Simultaneous optimization on the whole process and its energy supply, enabling Demand Side Response by leveraging process flexibility, thanks to MILP optimization method;
- Hourly optimization on up to seven days in advance;
- Optimization results are reviewed by the plant operators or energy managers, who are responsible of adapting production schedules and electricity nominations;
- Visual and interactive dashboards for results analysis.

6.1.3 Main limitations

- Asset models limited to linear or piecewise-linear models, due to the constraints imposed by the optimization method through Mixed Integer Linear Programming;
- Simultaneous optimization of energy & process can be computation-intensive in case of complex processes
- No direct automatic control of assets setpoints or power nominations;
- Long-term decision support and what-if scenarios not entirely supported yet

6.2 ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager

6.2.1 Short description

ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager is originally essentially an Energy Management System. Directly connected to all assets of the process, it is composed of 3 modules for energy management:

1. **Energy monitoring & reporting:** extensive supervision layer of all process assets energy consumption, in real-time based on data connections, including balance monitoring;
2. **Energy load forecasting:** day-ahead energy consumption planning per asset, based on appropriate prediction models (time-dependent, constant, based on production plan...), to estimate future energy consumption for accurate nominations;
3. **Energy optimization:** optimal scheduling and arbitrage of local power generation and power market transactions, considering contractual, economic and technical constraints.

However, this system on its own does not yet enable Demand-Side response, and can thereby not leverage process flexibilities such as production overcapacity, intermediate storage or arbitrage between multiple energy sources. However, ABB has been extending its Energy optimization module with an Industrial Demand-Side Management module, intended to support simultaneous or iterative optimization of production planning and energy management.

The demand-side management module (iDSM) performs holistic optimization of process loads to move consumption to off-peak hours and schedule assets start-ups and shutdowns, considering production requirements. These optimization results can be used either as a decision support for the operators, or directly control the assets setpoints through Advanced Process Control.

6.2.2 Main features

- Holistic Optimization with Mixed Integer Linear programming that **simultaneously considers all energy-consuming & energy-producing units**, and the option of purchasing/selling from/to the grid based on current prices.
- Optimization horizon ranging from a few minutes to **up to seven days** of production;
- Meant for daily use: production operators update each morning their section production schedule and validate the forecasted schedules of gas, electrical and steam demand.

- Integration of the iDSM module into the complete ABB Energy Management System provides a number of advantages:
 - o Connection to real-time measurement from the process control systems, facilitating load modelling and refining based on historical data;
 - o Operation schedule and actual real-time data are integrated in the same platform, and can be displayed together for comparison, to support the operators in detecting deviations. Similarly, historical actual data and future optimized data can be visualized on a common graph;
 - o Automatic re-calculation of optimal schedule when input data are updated;
 - o The tool can either be used as a decision-support system (production setpoint are manually changed by an operator), or the setpoints can be automatically controlled through Advanced Process Control (APC).
 - o Reactivity: as short-term optimization is enabled thanks to real-time data connectivity, production scheduler can not only create new schedules, but also update existing ones.
 - o Extensive visualization dashboards, built upon the energy management dashboards (actual past data, future optimal planning...)
- Possibility of performing “what-if” analyses to simulate the effect of structural changes without affecting actual process schedules.

6.2.3 Main limitations

- Simultaneous optimization of production schedule and electricity using MILP is **computation-intensive** and show **performance issues**, limiting the potential for short-term holistic optimization;
- **Not a standalone solution**: the iDSM module is only available as a part of the complete ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager;
- **No** mention of use of **market price forecasts** in the optimization.

6.3 Artelys Crystal Industry

6.3.1 Short description

Artelys Crystal Industry is a tool for industrial energy strategy optimization, used to design optimal operation management strategies and investment strategies for the energy system of industrial sites.

Regarding operation management strategies, the tool is meant to deliver optimal production plan strategy, and optimal bidding strategy against the DA electricity market, in order to reduce energy cost. Investment strategies consist in simulating the impact of new investments on these optimal operation management strategies (“what-if” scenarios), and assess the potential return of those investments.

The focus of Artelys Crystal Industry concerns the energy system of industrial processes, and it is hence not as such an industrial *Demand-Side Management* tool. On the one hand, the flexibility potential of the energy supply part can be leveraged, e.g. by defining an optimal arbitrage between multiple energy sources. On the other hand, this approach does not leverage intrinsic process flexibilities which can be used to shift the energy consumption to the cheapest hours (load shifting) by defining an optimal process production schedule. For example, the combination of production overcapacity and storage assets allows such load shifting, and this potential is not tackled by Artelys tool.

The design of optimal operation management strategies in Artelys Crystal Industry is based on a detailed model of the energy system at hand, including **local energy demand**, technical constraints of the **energy production assets**, **operational constraints** (such as safety/reserve) of the plant and a flowsheet structure representing the internal **energy flows** between assets. This model is fine-tuned based on historical data, by simulating the current energy strategies. The optimal strategy that is designed is then re-interpreted in a set of practical guidelines that can be used by field operators.

6.3.2 Main features

- Complete energy system model, considering local energy demand and production capacity and operational constraints:
 - o Built-in library of configurable assets: turbine, boiler, heat exchanger, heat pumps, electrolysers... with parameters such as capacity, yield, ramp rate, operating stages...
 - o Energy demand models for gas, power, heat, steam...
 - o Integration of contracts, markets and environmental constraints: power grid, gas prices, ancillary services, quotas on emissions...
 - o Time-dependent constraints (efficiency curves, operating durations, reserve constraints, start-up and shut-down ramps...) on various time scales (years, months, weeks, days, hours or less)
- Iterative fine-tuning of the model based on current strategy simulation, adapting the model parameters until results match historical data;
- Flexible optimization horizon with flexible granularity, extending the potential range of applications: from day-ahead power generation schedule and hourly bidding plan to year-ahead operation management strategy;
- Multi-core architectures that handles stochastic parameters through scenario variations);
- Multi-scenario handling and risk management, handling stochastic parameters such as load, market prices, outages through scenario variations, considering user risk margins;
- Interpretation of the optimal energy strategy in practical guidelines for daily use by operators: this makes
- "Study workflow" view facilitating the comparison of different simulation results based on customizable KPIs;
- Configurable views and graphs for display of production indicators;

6.3.3 Main limitations

1. Limited to the industrial process energy supply part: energy demand is modelled as a constraint to the model, and energy demand forecasts are required as inputs to the model;
2. Built-in asset library, based on specific asset types, makes more difficult the integration of assets that do not match with these types;
3. Stand-alone simulation tool, whose output must be interpreted before actual use by the relevant operator or energy manager.

6.4 Innovative features for BAMBOO DSS Tool

As BAMBOO DSS tool will be based upon N-SIDE Enertop, this section identifies the innovative features that could be added to the existing Enertop platform building upon the analysis performed of ABB's and Artelys's tools.

ABB's tool iDSM module shows various similarities with Enertop, as both are based on Mixed Integer Linear Programming for simultaneous optimization of process planning and energy supply to leverage flexibilities. Most of ABB's added features compared to Enertop are only possible thanks to the integration of the iDSM module into their Energy Management System, which enables or facilitates bilateral data connection to individual assets, direct control or optimal schedule real-time update. However, this also implies that ABB's Flexibility Optimization solution is not a "standalone" tool, limiting its potential reach and rapid replicability due to the high cost and effort of setting up the complete solution.

A summarized comparison of the 3 tools features is given in Table 5.

Regarding ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager, its major strength compared to Enertop is the integration with the Energy Management System that allows to combine the optimization with real-time reporting and data. Mainly, the following features could be thought of for BAMBOO DSS tool:

- Enhanced reactivity through real-time data acquisition based on a connection to the site local EMS;
- Advanced visualization dashboards, including if possible compared views of operation schedules against actual data;

On the other hand, Artelys Crystal Industry is more oriented towards long-term strategic and "what-if" analyses, which could provide inspiration for BAMBOO DSS tool:

- "What-if" scenarios with GUI that facilitates the comparison of multiple simulation runs
- Flexible optimization horizon up to a year
- Multi-scenario handling and risk management through scenario variations on stochastic parameters

In addition to these potential software features, the tool will integrate new modules and surrogate models of the technologies (ORC, industrial heat pump...) that will be developed in the frame of the BAMBOO project.

Table 5: Comparative summary of features of the three benchmarked flexibility valorization tools

Feature	N-SIDE Enertop	ABB cpmPlus	Artelys Crystal
<u>Modelling</u>			
Production process model (raw material supply, production rates, stocks, end-product demand...), to leverage production flexibility (storage, overcapacity, production scheduling...)	X		
Energy flows, generation & consumption models with various energy vectors (power, fuels, steam, heat...), to leverage energy flexibility (fuel switching, waste stream recycling...)	X	X	X
Forecasting of market price, RES production...	X		
Energy contracts & constraints models (power grid, quotas...)	X	X	X
<u>Optimization & results</u>			
Short-term hourly planning optimization (up to week-ahead)	X	X	X
Long-term strategy optimization (up to year-ahead)			X
"What-if" scenarios analysis (variations compared to actual)		X	X
<u>Data connection</u>			
Excel data import/export	X	X	X
Automatic data connection to external systems	X	X	
Real-time bilateral connection to assets control systems		X	
Integration within the plant EMS tool		X	
<u>GUI</u>			
Advanced visualization dashboards	X	X	X
Compared view "actual" vs "optimization results"		X	

7 CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS

In this report, a benchmarking of existing industrial flexibility management tools has been performed, towards the identification of innovative features that could be integrated in BAMBOO DSS tool. The first step has been identifying the relevant tools, which has highlighted that a limited number of commercial platforms are currently available to support industries to optimally leverage their processes flexibility. This first observation has confirmed the value of developing a holistic decision-support management tool for industrial processes flexibility valorization, in the scope of the BAMBOO project.

From this first identification phase, three commercial tools have been identified as relevant enough to investigate them further:

- N-SIDE Enertop (the basis on which BAMBOO DSS tool will be built);
- ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager Pro;
- Artelys Crystal Industry.

From the analysis of ABB and Artelys tools, several innovative features have been identified as potential improvements that could be brought to N-SIDE Enertop towards the development of BAMBOO DSS tool. Some example of such features are: extensive “what-if” scenarios simulation with flexible optimization horizon, advanced visualization dashboards & direct data connections.

It must be noted that this preliminary benchmarking analysis that has been performed, is mainly based on internet research, essentially from the suppliers’ own websites. A deeper and more accurate assessment would require to have an access to these tools. For this purpose, interactions with UPM and Tüpras shall be particularly relevant to receive their own feedback on their platform in use. More generally, as the next steps towards the design of BAMBOO DSS tool, discussions with consortium partners will be held in order to receive their feedbacks and expectations for the flexibility management tools.

8 REFERENCES

- [1] N-SIDE website - N-SIDE Enertop
<https://www.n-side.com/solution/industrial-energy-flexibility-optimization-2/>
- [2] ABB website - ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager
<https://new.abb.com/cpm/energy-manager>
- [3] Artelys website - Artelys Crystal Energy Planner
<https://www.artelys.com/en/applications/artelys-energy-planner>
- [4] Dexter Energy website
<https://www.dexterenergy.nl/>
- [5] Powel website
<https://www.powel.com/solutions/energy/>
- [6] Auto-grid website
<https://www.auto-grid.com/>
- [7] Senfal website
<https://senfal.com/en/>
- [8] ABB website - *Software helps shift production to times when energy is cheaper*
<https://new.abb.com/control-systems/industry-specific-solutions/pulp-and-paper/software-helps-shift-production-to-times-when-energy-is-cheaper>
- [9] ABB website - *Industrial demand-side energy management in Mayr-Melnhof Karton*
https://library.e.abb.com/public/1f3d9ee5c5e64188888734ead89a6097/success_story_Mayr-Melnhof%20Karton_ENG.pdf?x-sign=GeJXA+sr8XVDN0WKVR0c3q8JmYnOqAWZiL5K8kN7UO9t+YsiWP1nIsNJwd5rFZRq
- [10] ABB website - *New concept allowing industrial demand-side management tested live in steel production*
<https://new.abb.com/control-systems/industry-specific-solutions/metals/automatic-optimization-of-production-schedule-against-electricity-costs>
- [11] ABB website - *Case Study of Optimal Byproduct Gas Distribution in Integrated Steel Mill Using Multi-Period Optimization*
https://library.e.abb.com/public/4039246a7f29624585257b94004ab92b/Case%20Study%20of%20Optimal%20Byproduct%20Gas%20Distribution%20in%20Integrated%20Steel%20Mill%20Using%20Multi-Period%20Optimization_paper.pdf?x-sign=YZKWFgs1voPxd7C2BKnHUWsGKxi5QGPase/Ollx+HT45Efj9WXnDVSHZOYuTuEJT
- [12] Artelys Crystal Industry - Brochure
https://energie-industrie.com/media/Presentation/artelys_crystal_industry_2014_02_en_formata4_email_531152.pdf
- [13] CitInEs project - Publishable summary
<https://www.artelys.com/downloads/pdf/rapports-etudes/Project%20publishable%20summary.pdf>
- [14] Artelys website - Artelys Energy Planner
<https://www.artelys.com/fr/applications/artelys-energy-planner>

ANNEX 1 - DETAILED ANALYSES

A1.1 N-SIDE Enertop

ENERTOP is a modular energy flexibility platform combining forecast of electricity prices, modelling of process flexibilities and optimization algorithms with a user-friendly energy management visualization solution. Its main functionality is the hourly optimization of industrial process planning, according to forecasts of relevant market prices, considering all production constraints to advise the best operation strategy that will minimize the total cost of energy.

A1.1.1 ENERTOP modular structure

ENERTOP is structured into three layers composed of several modules providing the opportunity to easily customize ENERTOP Platform to client's need, and to plug-in other modules.

Figure 1: ENERTOP modular structure

A1.1.1.1 ENERTOP GUI

User-friendly web-interface composed of both an energy flexibility management solution and a visualization dashboard which create a communication point between ENERTOP and the users.

ENERTOP Flexibility Platform incorporates all actions linked to the leveraging of energy flexibilities, nomination optimization and energy flexibility activation acceptance/rejection.

Furthermore, the platform enables dashboard customization, providing quick insights on different energy data and savings.

Besides visualization aspects, ENERTOP platform also allows the user to export ENERTOP results and recommendations data in the form of excel reports to be handled by the clients according to their needs

Figure 2: Example of results visualization interface in ENERTOP

A1.1.1.2 ENERTOP Analytics (Flexibility Optimization Modules)

Within its core, ENERTOP benefits from advanced analytics modules aiming at providing its user with accurate forecasts of load and market, efficient mathematical modelling of assets, and advanced optimization algorithms for decision-aid making. The integrated advanced analytics modules are organized in 3 main types: descriptive (process modelling), predictive (market forecasting) and prescriptive (optimization algorithms) analytics. These modules are further described in Section A1.1.2 below.

A1.1.1.3 ENERTOP Data Connectors

Enertop Data Connection layer makes the interconnection between ENERTOP and the customer's Energy Data Management Platform in order to feed the optimization with the required data. A

standard Application Programming Interface (API) allows the site to connect easily ENERTOP with the different data sources under multiple formats. Customized Data integration can also be proposed in addition with a times and materials approach.

Figure 3: ENERTOP modular concept for a customized Energy Flexibility Optimization platform

A1.1.2 ENERTOP Modules

ENERTOP modules aim at valorizing the energy flexibilities with respect to multiple market opportunities (such as electricity day-ahead price volatility). This is done by modelling the industrial processes at the client site, and optimizing the clients' energy consumption and production considering the different market mechanism that the client is ready to interact with.

The "Process Model Configurator" allows to provide specifications of the processes to be optimized. A dedicated API is setup to allow automatic data retrieval from external platforms.

Based on these specifications, the process is modelled mathematically and optimized via the "Energy Flexibility Optimization" modules, for example day-ahead nomination optimization based on day-ahead prices forecast.

These optimization modules can be connected to the other plant systems in real time via Virtual Private Network (VPN), so as to communicate optimized planning, recommendations as well as resource usage and allocated transactions data. The VPN is used as a safety mean so as to encrypt data connections between ENERTOP modules and client systems.

Finally, the forecasting modules provide various forecasts, both external (e.g. electricity spot price) or internal (e.g. client load, local RES production). These forecasts are then used within the “Energy Flexibility Optimization” modules.

A1.1.3 Detailed Description of ENERTOP Modules

The following sections provide a detailed description of the ENERTOP Modules.

ENERTOP leverage the best of data analytics and optimization algorithms to help industrial companies capture the maximal value from their energy flexibilities, considering processes constraints and the different electricity markets opportunities.

To offer a comprehensive software platform for energy flexibility optimization, customized to the specific needs of each actor, three main modules relying on data analytics functionalities are combined:

Efficient mathematical modelling of flexibilities (process configurator) - Descriptive analytics

For different types of flexible consumers or producers, N-SIDE has developed flexibility-oriented mathematical models. These models allow representing the behavior of the assets, their flexibility opportunities (e.g. load or generation modulation, ON-OFF possibilities, fuel switching) and the different technical, economic and commercial constraints associated to them.

Figure 4: Process Configurator interface in ENERTOP

Accurate Forecasts & Constraints models (market forecasting) - Predictive analytics

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820771. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

ENERTOP price forecast module provide visibility for different electricity markets (e.g. day-ahead market). This visibility enables to find the market opportunities (e.g. price level, imbalance direction, etc.) for the next 15 minutes, hours or days. These algorithms for external market forecasting can also be combined with on-site forecasts of load or local generation (e.g. Photovoltaic (PV) or Wind).

Advanced Optimization Algorithms (leveraging flexibilities) - Prescriptive analytics

On different timeframes (investment, planning, intraday and real-time), our optimization modules allow to take the best decisions regarding the start-up/shut-down or modulation of flexible loads, the planning of flexible generators and the optimal management of storage. These decisions are based on the mathematical models of the flexible assets and on the forecasting of market opportunities.

Figure 5: Example of power consumption planning over a week based on DA price optimization

These different functionalities are combined to offer customized energy flexibility solutions that allow different market stakeholders to leverage their flexibilities in the best way using the most appropriate valorization means.

In the following subsections, we describe with more details the different ENERTOP analytics modules. The next section will then focus on how these modules are specifically combined to answer different flexibility valorization means in a fully integrated way using a combined optimization approach to optimize the revenue stacking.

A1.1.3.1 Flexible Process Modelling

The objective of ENERTOP is to maximize the value from energy flexibility assets (i.e. load, generator or storage). The key to this problem is having a good representation of these different assets to ensure that activation decisions will be made considering the real process constraints and flexibility opportunities. This mathematical representation of the assets includes:

- Their flexibility levers i.e. the possibility to modify their load or generation profile

- Their technical constraints like the ramping constraints, the ON-OFF procedures, the minimal and maximal output levels, the needed notice period before activation, the minimal or maximal duration of an activation, etc.
- Their economic impacts like the operating costs at different production levels, the activation cost, the opportunity cost of production loss, etc.
- Their commercial/planning constraints like the required quantities to produce over a day or the order book to be satisfied.

In the rest of this section, the main types of models available within ENERTOP are described, as well as the different process features represented by each of these models:

Flexible Loads Models

ENERTOP modelling module for flexible loads is used to represent key industrial processes, compressors, HVAC, heat pumps and many more.

For each represented load, the corresponding opportunities are modelled: load shifting (shifting consumption at a better moment), load shedding (stop the process when electricity prices are too high or when received compensation is sufficiently high), load scheduling (produce energy intensive products when prices are cheaper) or fuel switching (switch between electricity and other fuels depending on price opportunities).

The model of the process can include dedicated constraints taken from the large library of constraint of ENERTOP such as a ramping time when starting or stopping the machine, or when changing the utilization mode. It is also possible to specify that the process should be working during a certain period of the day, needs a minimum duration for the machine to be turned on or off, or should be operating simultaneously with another machine of the ecosystem.

Using the right set of constraints ENERTOP can ensure that the planning and activation decisions of the flexible load are compatible with the process realities

Flexible Generators Models

ENERTOP allows to model different type of flexible electricity generation assets like cogeneration units, diesel generators or fuel cells.

These models combine the technical parameters of the asset (efficiency at different power outputs, start-up/shut down procedure, ramping constraints, minimal up time constraints, etc.) with the economical parameters (cost of fuel, operating costs, marginal cost of production).

For CHP units, the model also includes the heat demand from the other processes, potential flexibility in the power to heat ratio and a specific library of constraints for CHP components (e.g. gas engine, gas turbine, boiler, steam turbines, etc.).

Storage Models

ENERTOP allows to model different types of storage assets, whether storage is directly applied to electricity (e.g. batteries) or electricity-equivalent products (e.g. the cold in a refrigerated warehouse or intermediate product storage in an industrial process).

The storage module includes the modelling of the storage levels depending on the activation/modulation decisions (inputs and outputs), on the storage constraints (e.g. minimal, targeted and maximal levels) and on the storage efficiency (e.g. temperature of a fridge will increase over time if the compressors are not running).

Additionally, the valorization of the storage level at the end of the optimization time period is considered.

RES flexibility models

Even if the normal production levels of wind turbines and solar panels cannot be controlled as it depends on stochastic parameters like the weather, the possible curtailment of these assets has to be considered as a flexibility option. ENERTOP RES flexibility models allows to model the curtailment possibilities of these assets, the associated technical constraints and the opportunity cost of not-produced electricity.

Electricity Contract Models

To allow an efficient use of flexibility assets, different contractual elements have to be considered:

- Composition of electricity procurement between hedged/clicked volumes and volumes impacted by spot price
- Taxes, transmission and distribution costs for electricity off-take and injection
- Contractual maximal injection and off-take at the connection point with transmission or distribution network
- Commitment on reserve markets and other ancillary services
- These different parameters and constraints are modeled in ENERTOP and considered for the activation/modulation decisions of the flexible assets.

A1.1.3.2 Forecast Module

If it is of key importance to model in an accurate way the different on-site flexible assets, it is also crucial to model and forecast the different flexibility opportunities and risks faced by the industrial site. These forecasts will serve as a key input for the decisions to be taken on the different assets. On top of these market forecasts, it is also important to consider how the site interacts with these markets, that is the contractual aspects and the grid constraints of the site.

Many different forecasts can be integrated in ENERTOP depending on the project scope and the considered markets. The two most usual forecasts considered are listed below, and detailed in the next paragraphs.

- Forecast of Electricity Market Price and Opportunities for day-ahead market
- Forecast of on-site load and RES generation.

Day-ahead electricity price forecast

One of the objectives of ENERTOP is to deliver an optimal planning both in terms of consumption and generation of electricity, based on the spot electricity prices.

When the site has to provide a nomination of the hourly net load for the next day and/or when some flexible processes have to be planned one or two days in advance, it is crucial to base the planning decisions on a spot electricity forecast that provides an accurate visibility about the spot electricity prices in the coming days.

ENERTOP contains a forecasting model that computes an estimation of the electricity spot price at the hourly level for the next 7 days. To obtain the price forecast included in ENERTOP, advanced machine learning techniques are applied on different sources including the

- Electricity historical prices
- Electric network information and status (power plant maintenance, congestion of the grid, etc.)
- Weather forecast, such as the temperature which can influence the demand of the overall market, but also wind and sunshine forecast which drives the RE generation on the grid.

A1.1.3.3 Energy Flexibility Optimization

ENERTOP is a decision-making tool allowing to make the best flexibility decisions on different time frames (strategic investment, daily/weekly planning, bidding on markets and real-time), but is essentially focused on day-ahead hourly optimization. Leveraging the mathematical representations of the flexible assets and the different forecasts and constraints models described in the two-previous subsection, ENERTOP uses advanced optimization algorithms to activate the best flexibility assets at the best moment and to valorize them on the best market.

The main optimization module of Enertop is the Day-Ahead planning optimization. The **planning** optimization module aims at generating optimal planning for the flexible loads, flexible generators and storage assets considering as time horizon the next hours and the next days.

This planning optimization module allows in particular the industrial site to define optimal nomination for the next day. Considering the forecast for the spot price, the day-ahead forecast for the on-site load and generation and the availability of the different flexibility assets, ENERTOP will schedule the flexible assets in order to consume, produce and store electricity at the best moment. This results in optimized nominations for the next 24 hours.

In order to avoid myopic planning, the time horizon of the optimization is set to a few days (e.g. one week). This way, electricity price and weather forecasts can be used in order to determine the best possible strategy for the following day, considering what will probably happen during the few days after. Knowing this information, the storages can be correctly used and valorized at the end of the planning period.

The optimization algorithm receives as input the different forecast predictions (spot price, re-generation) and the modelling of the energy ecosystem with its properties, restrictions and demands. The objective is then to minimize the cost while satisfying all the demands under the described restrictions.

The output of this tool presents, for each time step, the planning of each equipment, the local electricity production, the overall energy needs and purchases as well as the state of the storages.

In periods of high electricity spot prices, ENERTOP will reduce the net load of the site or even maximize the reinjection on the grid by increasing locally produce electricity, leveraging previously stored electricity and reducing consumption of flexible loads. In the opposite when spot prices are low, ENERTOP will push for electricity consumption directly from the grid and store as much as possible electricity for later use.

A1.2 ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager

A1.2.1 Description & main functionalities

ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager is an integrated Energy Management System (EMS) built upon three main modules:

1. Energy Monitoring & Reporting module

- Collection & visualization of real-time energy consumption data
- Integrates energy contracts (pricing) information
- Energy consumption reports

2. Energy Load Planning (forecasting) module

- Load scheduling (forecasting) based on production planning
- Calculates energy consumption schedules, based on multiple variables

3. Energy Optimization module

- Optimizes the supply of required electrical power through active participation in the DA market and/or optimal planning of power supply sources

Figure 6: The 3 modules of ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager Pro

A1.2.1.1 Energy Monitoring & Reporting module

This module integrates most “usual” features of an industrial EMS tool:

- Real-time view of energy performance:
 - Identification of baseline for energy utilization
 - Comparison of actual consumption against baseline
 - Corrective actions advising in case of deviations
- Integrated features (non-exhaustive):
 - Determine specific energy consumption
 - Monitor energy consumption
 - Simulate production scenarios
 - Reconcile energy bills
 - Define energy reports
 - Real-time power balance management
- Dashboards:
 - KPIs (aggregated view and trends, on selectable time horizons): Production, Energy, SEC (Specific Energy Consumption), Costs, CO₂
 - Analyses: Correlation, Stability, Distribution...
 - Supports the exchange of information from the operator to the facility manager, highlighting savings potentials
 - Illustrative examples are provided as Screenshots in Figure 7 below

A1.2.1.2 Load Planning / Forecasting module

This module calculates (forecasts) the energy consumption planning of the industrial process, based on the assets production planning (operating schedule):

- Energy consumption forecasting:
 - Accurate forecast of energy consumption, for right nomination
 - Comparison of estimated consumption compared to contractual limits
 - Consumption monitoring, ensuring not exceeding peak load conditions
- Calculation method:
 - Each consumer power need is forecasted through an appropriate prediction method, defined based on historical energy consumption data.
 - Multiple prediction methods are possible:
 - Time-dependent profiles
 - Self-adaptive profiles
 - Based on production plan
 - Production grade dependent profiles
 - Production cycle dependent profiles
 - Constant load
 - Multiple energy types are supported (electrical, steam, gas)
 - Multiple scenarios for forecast are supported
 - Interface with energy market
- Dashboards:
 - Compared display of actual and forecasted energy consumption, per consumer
 - Drill-down per consumer
 - Energy vectors other than electricity are also included (steam, gas)
 - Illustrative examples are provided as Screenshots in Figure 8 below
- Possibility to use the module for simulation through modification of the parameters, without affecting the real system data (e.g. new purchase/sales contracts, unit operating schedules...)

Figure 7: Illustrative screenshots of ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager - Monitoring & Reporting module

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820771. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

Figure 8: Illustrative screenshots of ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager - Load Forecasting module

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820771. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

A1.2.1.3 Energy Optimization module (Economic Flow Network)

This module is used to optimize the total cost of energy to supply the predicted energy consumption, through active participation in the DA market and/or own energy production units:

- Hourly optimization of energy supply for the scheduled power consumption, via:
 - Efficient use of internally generated energy (generation)
 - Energy purchased from the utilities / markets (purchase)
- Considers the cost of deviations from the committed load curve
- Manages exchanges of energy with the grid (purchase / sale)
- Calculation method: Economic Flow Network
 - Energy purchase planning is based on balancing energy flows in each balance area with minimal total costs

Planning and scheduling tools

- Load Planning to predict and schedule energy demand
- Economic Flow Network model to balance energy demand and supply at optimal costs
- What-If Scenarios and Simulation to evaluate and compare alternative operating scenarios

Real time balance monitoring tools

- Load planning to predict short term consumption and imbalance with supply plan
- Power monitoring to predict current period consumption

Energy monitoring and reporting

Day-ahead planning and optimization

Benefits:

- Employ optimal power resources
- Lower power price by sending load schedules to power supplier
- Avoid expensive power by demand scheduling

Real time monitoring and reporting

Benefits:

- Lower balancing power and cost
- Lower demand charges and penalty fees
- Higher energy efficiency and reduced carbon footprint

Figure 9: Schematic representation of ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager Pro optimization functionalities

A1.2.2 iDSM (Industrial Demand-Side Management)

Current developments (pilot projects) are being added to the **Energy Optimization module** to support a holistic optimization of energy use and supply, including **Demand-Side response**:

- Optimization of process loads based on energy price
 - Move consumption to off-peak hours
 - Schedule start-ups and operating cost
 - Support for multiple scenarios and energy types
- Operating modes:
 - Decision support for the operators, who manually adapt the assets setpoints
 - Automatic production setpoints control through Advanced Process Control (APC)

As explained in the figure below, the goal of ABB is to evolve the system from a sequential optimization of Energy supply based on a defined production schedule, to a holistic (simultaneous or iterative) optimization of Production planning and Energy supply based on production requirements and power prices (Demand-Side response).

Figure 10: Traditional sequential approach compared to a collaborative approach of optimization

Figure 11: Illustrative screenshot of ABB cpmPlus Energy Manager - iDSM module

A1.2.2.1 Case: Flexible production optimization in the Pulp & Paper industry

ABB has run a pilot project for optimal timing of electricity consumption based on power price fluctuations. The main features of the pilot project are:

- Holistic Optimization that simultaneously considers all energy-consuming & energy-producing units, and the option of purchasing / selling from/to the grid based on current prices.
- Also includes other production units, considering steam demand, steam production capacity and cost, paper machines production plan and production limits
- The optimization is based on a pre-specified pulp/paper production schedule
- The scientific challenge arises in simultaneously optimizing the production schedule and the electricity purchase strategy. Mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) techniques represent a very promising way to arrive at holistic optimization solutions to problems like this that have partly competing targets.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820771. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

BAMBOO

A1.2.2.2 Case: *Byproduct gas distribution optimization in the Steel industry*

ABB developed new concepts allowing industrial demand-side management (iDSM) by automatic optimization of the production schedule against the electricity costs, using Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) techniques. The first step toward the iDSM solution was to investigate the use of monolithic models for the integration schemes, with ABB Economic Flow Network modelling tool (EFN). In this approach, the continuous-time (exact) melt-shop scheduling model has been refined to consider both the electricity price as well as deviations from a committed load curve.

The production scheduler is able to automatically and optimally create a new schedule, or manually update an existing one, for up to seven days of production within just a few minutes. The system is flexible enough to support different melt shop configurations, as well as to include all other information necessary - such as processing, transportation, setup and cleanup times - to generate a feasible production schedule. It also considers maintenance plans, the current status of the melt shop and availability of different equipment, due dates, penalties for lateness and violation of holdup times between stages in the process, etc. In addition, the steel plant created a Web-based GUI that allows the user to flexibly select what to optimize and schedule.

Features:

- Compared visualization of current production status of each unit versus the optimal solution planning.
- The GUI supports operators to initiate actions to minimize losses and production delays - for example, reschedule or postpone production slightly due to a high electricity price. The new scheduling system is not only linked to other internal IT systems such as ERP and process control, but also to the external day-ahead electricity market, in order to dynamically cater for volatile electricity prices.
- Simulation and what-if analyses are supported

Theoretically, this holistic-model-based optimization may lead to a so called global optimum, ie, the best possible solution with respect to both the production and electricity costs. However, holistic models are very often complicated or impossible to solve within a reasonable time, so some refinement is required. However, holistic models are very often complicated or impossible to solve within a reasonable time, so some refinement is required. This basic approach is not efficient for more complex instances. Therefore, various alternative approaches have also been looked at including other modelling philosophies - eg, resource-task network - as well as decomposition algorithms. The problem of simultaneously optimizing energy management aspects and production planning needs has still not been completely solved and researchers are currently trying to find ways to handle this in realistic production environments.

A1.3 Artelys Crystal Industry

Artelys is offering a various range of platforms for different applications, such as local energy strategy with Crystal City, transmission capacity expansion with Crystal Super Grid or activities and resources planning with Crystal Resource Optimizer. Related to energy flexibility optimization, they developed the tool Crystal Industry as part of the project CitInEs. Today, this tool does not seem to be offered under this name anymore, and appears to have been replaced by Crystal Energy Planner. As these two names seem to cover approximately the same tool, they are both analyzed in this section but the conclusions are drawn considering them the same tool.

A1.3.1 CitInEs Project - Crystal Industry

Artelys Crystal Industry was developed in the CitInEs project as a multi-scale and multi-energy calculation platform to help large industrial complexes optimize their energy strategies:

- Simulate, assess and compare energy investment programs.
- Assess financial and environmental long-term risks and propose robust energy schemes to face fuel and CO₂ price uncertainties.
- Define a sustainable, efficient and safe energy strategy.

The tool is dedicated to the design of **optimal operation management strategies** for the **energy system** of industrial sites, considering **operational, economic and environmental constraints**. It is based on a model of the energy system, and a calibration based on historical data. Because the tool is optimizing the energy management, existing flexibilities in the energy system of the plant are also valorized.

More specifically, the platform is used to derive practical guidelines for **optimal production plan strategy** and **optimal bidding strategy against the DA electricity market**. Its usage is structured around two different types of studies, respectively on **management strategy** and **investment strategy**.

Functionalities

- Energy system modelling based on the built-in Asset library
- Parameters fine-tuning based on historical data
- Computation of optimized strategies satisfying technical and operational constraints
- Design of operation management and investment strategies
- Comparison of various strategies in terms of environmental and economic impacts

Use cases

- Design of optimal operational management strategies for energy cost reduction
- Leveraging of industrial flexibility on the power markets
- Design of new strategies following regulatory or economic changes
- Cost-benefit analysis and environmental impact of investment potentials
- Evaluation of the potential of storage assets or capacity markets

Figure 12: Scheme of the decision support tools developed within the CitInEs project

A1.3.1.1 Functionalities

A1.3.1.1.1 Management strategy study

The goal of the management strategy study is to define the best possible strategy for the operational management of the process, optimized on the level of its energy procurement.

Practically, it consists of 4 stages:

1. Model of the energy systems, including:
 - a. **local energy demand**;
 - b. technical constraints of the **energy production assets**;
 - c. **operational constraints** (such as safety/reserve) of the plant;
 - d. flowsheet structure representing the internal **energy flows** between assets.
2. Historical replay
 - a. Integration of historical data;
 - b. Simulation of the current strategy for data reconciliation (stages 1-2 are performed iteratively to remove any discrepancy between simulated and historical data).
3. Optimization
 - a. Computation of an optimized operation strategy;
 - b. If the "optimal" strategy solution highlights missing constraints in the model, stages 1-2-3 are re-iterated.

4. Future strategy

- a. Re-interpretation of the optimized strategy in simple and practical guidelines that can be used by field operators.

For industrial plants, the outcome of an operational management study is the application of new management rules by the operators, which will help improving the specific key performance indicators considered during the study.

A1.3.1.1.2 Investment study

The goal of the investment study is to assess the potential gains brought by potential investments (“what-if” scenarios) in comparison with each other and with the “as-is” situation.

The workflow used to perform an investments study is similar to the operational management study, except that stages 3 and 4 are used to compare different asset portfolios, computing the optimal operational strategy of each investment scenario.

A1.3.1.2 Features

A1.3.1.2.1 Plant model and representation

The following elements are available to build the complete plant model in the platform:

- **Assets**, selected from a built-in **library** (turbines, boilers, storage units, heat exchangers...) and **fine-tuned** (capacities, yields, ramps, operating stages...)
- Energy demands (gas, power, heat, steam)
- Contracts and markets (power grid and market, gas prices, reserve markets)
- Time-dependent constraints (efficiency curves, operating durations, reserve constraints, start-up and shut-down ramps...) on various time scales (years, months, weeks, days, hours or less)
- Detailed costs: fluctuating fuel costs, start-up and shut-down costs...

A1.3.1.2.2 Time-dependent optimization and simulation engine

Artelys Crystal Industry can be used in three different modes:

- **Historical replay**: visualize and analyze past production strategies, and use the historical production measures to reconcile them with the plant model (generate missing data, detect inconsistencies and eliminate measurement errors) and validate it.
- **Optimization**: determine the production plan that minimizes the total cost of energy, over a chosen time period (e.g. one year) and granularity (e.g. one hour). It uses multi-core architectures to handle stochastic parameters (through scenario variations). This mode also support what-if scenario analyses.
- **Custom strategy simulation**: specific operational strategies can be integrated in the planning computations, considering for example price threshold strategies, merit order policies of monthly budget of emissions, fuel, activation time...

A1.3.1.2.3 User interface

The GUI of Artelys Crystal Industry includes a “study workflow” view, displayed in Figure 13, where are summarized the information of all simulation runs. Multiple simulations results can be directly compared based on this view.

The visualization tools for analysis of simulation input data and results provides indicators that can be customized. Multiple types of views and graphs are available for display of the production indicators, with configurable view controls (filters, colorings, synchronization...). The simulation comparison views facilitate the comparison and assessment of multiple management strategies.

	History	Reconciled history	Optimized strategy	Threshold strategy	Add Simulation Type
May 2011 2011-05-01 2011-05-06 Time steps: 60 min	StudyDemo (May 2011-History)	StudyDemo (May 2011-Reconciled history)	StudyDemo (May 2011-Optimized strategy)	StudyDemo (May 2011-Threshold strategy)	
August 2011 2011-08-17 2011-08-22 Time steps: 60 min	StudyDemo (August 2011-History)	StudyDemo (August 2011-Reconciled history)	StudyDemo (August 2011-Optimized strategy)	StudyDemo (August 2011-Threshold strategy)	
November 2011 2011-11-28 2011-11-30 Time steps: 60 min	StudyDemo (November 2011-History)	StudyDemo (November 2011-Reconciled history)	StudyDemo (November 2011-Optimized strategy)	StudyDemo (November 2011-Threshold strategy)	
February 2012 2012-02-04 2012-02-09 Time steps: 60 min	StudyDemo (February 2012-History)	StudyDemo (February 2012-Reconciled history)	StudyDemo (February 2012-Optimized strategy)	StudyDemo (February 2012-Threshold strategy)	
May 2012 2012-05-11 2012-05-16 Time steps: 60 min	StudyDemo (May 2012-History)	StudyDemo (May 2012-Reconciled history)	StudyDemo (May 2012-Optimized strategy)	StudyDemo (May 2012-Threshold strategy)	

Figure 13: Artelys Crystal Industry - Study workflow view

A1.3.1.3 Case: Tüpras Izmit refinery

In the scope of the CitInEs project, Artelys Crystal Industry was applied to Tüpras Izmit refinery, which includes power systems supplying electricity and steam to the hydrocarbon refining process, and is also connected to the power grid. The specificities of that project were:

- 9 energy vectors: natural gas, refinery gas, fuel oil, electricity, water and steam;
- >10 assets including boilers, steam turbines, gas turbines and letdown stations;
- 1-year time horizon with 1-hour granularity;
- Linear & piecewise-linear yield models;
- Constraints on Min/Max capacities varying over time and fuel-dependent;
- Safety reserve constraints
- Combustible mixes constraints

The operational management strategies that were evaluated covered bidding guidelines, and production guidelines.

It is important to note that the simulations were limited to the “Power Plant” part of the refinery, considering the power demand forecast as an input. Although it is therefore not really optimizing the industrial process operation, the principles used could be replicated to an industrial process Demand-Side Management DSS tool.

A1.3.1.3.1 Bidding guideline

The bidding guidelines were designed to optimize, on a daily basis, the Day-Ahead market bidding strategy. The main inputs used by the platform are:

- Fixed Risk margins on bid price & quantity
- Fixed costs (natural gas & water)
- Fixed unit capacities
- Forecasts of refinery demand of electricity and steam

The main output of the bidding guideline is an **hourly bidding plan for the next day** (BUY and SELL bids), on which the user may apply some margins if required.

Every day before noon, the user of the platform would provide to the platform the refinery demand prevision and update other parameters if required, and place the bids on the market based on the bidding guideline output. At the end of the day, the user will issue the electricity supply/delivery schedule from/to the grid for the next day based on the acceptance of his bids.

A1.3.1.3.2 Production guideline

Next to the bidding guideline, the platform is also providing production guideline. The optimized production guidelines are computed one time (see A1.3.1.1.1) and summarized in an Excel workbook. These optimal production guidelines are defined as a set of a limited number of **production states**, each corresponding to a certain state of the whole process. Each state corresponds to a list of the running units, list of min/max targets (fixed production rate) and list of control points (which assets control a certain demand), as exemplified below. The possible transitions between states, and their triggers, are also defined.

Figure 14: Example of production states and transitions in Artelys Crystal Industry

A1.3.2 Crystal Energy Planner

On the website of Artelys, there is no mention of Artelys Crystal Industry; instead of “Artelys Crystal Energy Planner” is available with similar features, but much oriented towards energy system optimization. Artelys Crystal Energy Planner optimizes the short- and medium-term operational management strategies of power production asset (thermal, gaz, hydro...).

Functionalities

- Automatic data import/export (Excel, database, web)
- Easy results analysis
 - Results visualization for operational management
 - Graphs specific indicators (sales and generation, stock levels, market blocks...)
 - Detailed or aggregated configurable KPIs
 - Reports automation and export
- Complete modelling of the energy system
 - Built-in asset library:
 - Production assets (thermal, hydro, renewable)
 - Storage
 - Power consumption assets (heat pumps, boilers, electrolysers)
 - Load, markets and contracts:
 - Power and ancillary markets: energy, reserves, real-time constraints based on DA nomination
 - Energy and spinning-reserve demand
 - Supply constraints: fuel costs, supply contracts
 - Environmental constraints: limits, costs, taxes, quotas on emissions
- Multi-scenario handling and risk management
 - Generation plan are optimized considering several scenarios, thereby making the decisions based on several forecasts for load, market prices, outages...
- Various timescales optimization (see Figure 15 below)
- Interactive visualization dashboards (see Figure 16 below)

Figure 15: Potential applications and timescales of Artelys Crystal Energy Planner

Figure 16: Illustrative screenshots of Artelys Crystal Energy Planner visualization dashboards

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820771. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

